

DEVELOPMENT OF VOLITIONAL QUALITIES OF PERSONALITY IN CHILDREN OF JUNIOR SCHOOL AGE THROUGH SPORTS

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Annotation: The article is devoted to the study of the volitional qualities of a personality in children of primary school age, involved and not involved in sports. In the study, the technique "Unsolvable problem" was used. The study was conducted with children of primary school age. The results of the study showed that children involved in sports are more determined and try to achieve their goals, even when this goal is impossible.

Key words: personality, will, volitional qualities, junior schoolchildren, sport, unsolvable task.

Introduction. In modern conditions, for the development of a new favorable society, purposeful, hardy, harmoniously and comprehensively developed personalities are needed [1, 2, 3]. Therefore, the following question arises: will today's person be ready to overcome the obstacles that await him on the path of life, will he have enough strength, perseverance and enthusiasm to overcome any difficulties? Various personality traits play an important role in this, but the qualities of will stand out especially: perseverance, self-confidence, patience, endurance [4, 5, 6]. Not a single life problem of a person is solved without the participation of the volitional qualities of the individual.

The main task of the modern school is the development of the student's personality, his activity and independence, the maximum realization of his creative potential in order to promote his comprehensive and harmonious development, intellectual growth, as well as the formation of mental processes [3, 5, 7]. The learning process is more effective if the student shows volitional qualities not only

at school, but also in extracurricular activities. Extracurricular activities, as well as the activities of students within the framework of the lessons, are aimed at achieving results, as well as mastering the main educational program. It allows the child to choose an area of interest, develop his abilities, and also become a stable base for the formation of volitional qualities of the individual [9, 11, 14].

One of the main ways to develop the volitional qualities of the personality of children is sports. The main volitional qualities of athletes are: purposefulness, initiative, determination, courage, self-control, perseverance, steadfastness [8, 12, 13, 14]. Regardless of the type of sports activity, an athlete needs all developed volitional qualities in the aggregate, and therefore their comprehensive education should be included in the main content of an athlete's training. To educate the volitional qualities of the character of a young athlete, along with the general factors of education, the whole complex of basic means and methods of training is used [16, 18, 19].

In this case, the orientation of the child's activity towards overcoming the growing difficulties is of decisive importance, which in turn helps the child to form such an incentive as "the will to win" [17, 20].

These methods of "Unsolvable problem" most actively reveal one of the stable characteristics of the personality - an emotional reaction to the difficulty, an indicator of which is the refusal to solve the problem. In addition, the difficulty is always associated with the manifestation of the volitional qualities of a person. To study the volitional effort of schoolchildren, it is necessary to use a situation in which the student could work hard. In this case, the time for solving the problem and the number of attempts to solve it can be a quantitative characteristic of volitional effort. The reason for the refusal, the different behavior of students can be used for a qualitative analysis of the relationship between volitional qualities and emotionality of students.

Pictures were used in the study. The first was simple, it consisted of one figure, which was assembled quite easily, so that this task did not seem difficult for students. The second picture was a little more difficult than the previous one, as it consisted of more elements. The third picture was the most difficult, and also was not assembled, because it was missing one fragment. The complexity of collecting the third picture consisted not only in the fact that it could not be completed to the end, but also in the fact that it contained a sufficiently large number of elements. The analysis of the results of collecting the third picture is the most important. He showed that 4 groups of schoolchildren stood out according to the time of trying to collect the third picture: 1 group spent 3-5 minutes on collecting an uncollected picture; group 2 5 - 7 minutes; group 3 7 - 10 minutes; 4 group more than 10 minutes.

The subjects of the 1st group (20%) spent the least amount of time trying to collect the third picture. This speaks of poorly developed volitional qualities, such as perseverance and patience. In the subjects of the 4th group (26%), the time spent on collecting the same picture was the maximum, which shows that perseverance, patience and perseverance in this group of children are most developed compared to the rest. In subjects 2 (24%) and 3 groups (30%), these volitional qualities are developed at an average level. The subjects of the 4th group, whose time spent on collecting the third picture was the maximum, in 71% of cases are athletes.

Behavior analysis, after a failed attempt to collect the picture, showed the following. In group 1, 46% of children were upset that they could not complete the task. Some children from the second group (36%) of the subjects showed aggression. 18% of students remained passive to failure when trying to complete the task. The first and third groups of subjects blamed circumstances (19%) and the experimenter or "creator" of the picture (12%) for failure. Most often, these students have a high level of development of courage, independence, efficiency

and stubbornness, but they cannot use these qualities when overcoming difficulties. The second group of subjects (37%) blamed themselves for the failure.

They are distinguished by a weak development of volitional qualities, most often children are indecisive and not confident in their abilities. This group of children is characterized by emotional instability, which affects the quality of performing various tasks. Students of this group are lost when faced with difficulties and, as a rule, have a low level of development of such strong-willed qualities as independence, determination, organization, perseverance. The fourth group of subjects (32%) indicated an objective reason for failure. They are emotionally stable when faced with difficulties, enterprising, persistent, active, independent, and have adequate behavior. This group of subjects has a high level of development of volitional qualities.

In most cases (53%), the subjects wanted to try to reassemble the picture, which indicates that this group of children has developed purposefulness, determination and courage. The second group of students, who refused to re-attempt to collect the picture, made up 47% of the total. In most cases, they are indecisive, and also do not know how to achieve their goals, overcoming difficulties.

The analysis showed that 81% of the children who decided to try to collect the failed picture again go in for sports, and only 19% of the children who also made a second attempt are not athletes.

According to the indicators of behavior during the experiment and the reason for refusing to re-attempt to collect the third picture, students involved and not involved in sports differ statistically significantly ($P=0.0026$; $P=0.0041$, respectively). Analysis of the repeated collection of the third picture between students involved in sports and not involved in sports showed that they differed highly statistically ($P=0.00003$).

Conclusions. Thus, according to the results of our study, it was revealed that for all the studied indicators there is a difference between students who go in for sports and those who do not.

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